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**A STUDY ON WORKLIFE BALANCE OF
EMPLOYEES WITH REFERENCE TO MANAGLORE
REFINERIES PETROCHEMICAL LIMITED (MRPL)**

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INTRODUCTION

Work life balance refers to the effective to the management of multiple responsible at work, at home, and in the other aspects of life. It is an issue that is important both to the organization and to employees. In the current economic scenario, organizations are hard pressed for higher productivity and need employees with improved work-life balance as employees with better work-life balance will contribute more meaningfully towards the organization growth and success, this issue has come to the fore due to multitude of changes in the workplace, in employees demographics and in the family sphere.

DEFINITION OF WORK-LIFE BALANCE

“Work” and “life” have been rather loosely defined in literature where work is paid employment and life is everything outside of the formal employment but is usually used to connote the realm of family or home life. The concept is loosely defined and is seen to derive from sexual/gender division of labor and this renders WLB is equally important for both men and women, and that men are equally burdened by the work and family responsibilities. His conceptualization still remains narrow in that through the earlier rhetoric of WLB for working mothers has been criticized, it still remains in the purview of work and family.

CURRENT SCENARIO

Work-life balance has been addressed by some employers and has been seen as a benefit to them. Research by Kenexa Institute in 2007 shows that those employees who were more favorable towards their organization's efforts to support work-life balance also indicated a much lower intent to leave the organization, greater pride in their organization, a willingness to recommend it as a place to work and higher overall job satisfaction.

Employers can offer a range of different programs and initiatives, such as flexible working arrangements in the form of part-time, casual and telecommuting work. More proactive. Employers can provide compulsory leave, strict maximum hours and foster an

environment that encourages employees not to continue working after hours. It is generally only highly skilled workers that can enjoy such benefits as written in their contracts, although many professional fields would not go so far as to discourage workaholic behavior. Unskilled workers will almost always have to rely on bare minimum legal requirements. Therefore it is important for employees to maintain a healthy balance between work and their private lives. This helps them to achieve their personal and professional goals as well as the organization they are working for. Work life balance is not a problem to be solved. It is an ongoing issue to be managed.

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

1. To study the impact of work life balance initiatives on productivity.
2. To analyze the factors which affect work life balance adversely and their level of influence on individual.
3. To know the initiatives of the company to ensure work life balance in the organization.
4. To assess and evaluate the impact of work life balance of employees and suggest the specific recommendation for the betterment.
5. To know how the organization manage the manage the employees benefits and service programmer.

STATEMENT OF A PROBLEM

The articulation of work and life, case as work-life balance, has become a key feature of much current government, practitioner and academic debate. It is believed that balancing a successful career with a personal or family life can be challenging and impact on a person's satisfaction in their work and personal life's 4 roles. Dundas argued that work-life balance is about effectively managing the juggling act between paid work and all other activities that are important to people such as family community activity, voluntary between workplace's needs and personal life's needs is perceived as an important issue among workers globally and academics in higher education institution were not excluded. Work life balance has been studied within the context of business, for-profit organization. It has also been explored within higher education organization.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The design of any research project requires considerable attention to the research methods and the proposed data analysis. The research method documents describe a number of components required for fundamental proposal.

Primary Data

The respondents were administered with work life balance questionnaire constructed and the data obtained were subjected to statistical analysis.

Secondary Data

The secondary data for the study is collected from websites, books, magazines etc.

RESEARCH DESIGN

The design of any research project requires considerable attention to the research methods and the proposed data analysis. The research method documents described a number of components required for fundamental proposal.

Sample Size

The sample for the present study constituted 70 employees of Mangalore Refineries Petroleum Ltd (MRPL) Mangalore, Karnataka India. Non-probability, convenience sampling technique is considered to select the sample for study.

Sample Area

The sample area selected for the study is Mangalore Refineries Petroleum Ltd (MRPL) Mangalore.

Sample Element

The sample elements considered for the study are the employees of MRPL.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

1. The focus groups and interviews conducted in this study will help apply new findings to contexts outside the communications industry, leading to information about the effect of work life balance organizational culture that is transferable to organizations and the research to obtain an understanding of employee behavior through intensive group interviews.
2. Some participant experienced work life balance as a serious problem, whilst for others it was of little concern. Participants, who experienced their work life.
3. Balance as a concern, generally reported that, although they could cope reasonably well with it, there were times that became problematic.
4. It also happened that at some stage in the participants, working lives, work-lives, work-life balance had presented; however, they had now made a conscious effort to manage and control it.
5. As with most things in life, moderation is the key. People who are constantly tied to their jobs deal with the symptoms of stress and burnout.
6. Overworked employees are more likely to suffer health problems, more likely to be absent and / or sick, less efficient, less sociable, and overall more difficult to work with. It is in the best interest of both the employees and employer to avoid these pitfalls through smart human resource management.

DATA ANALYSIS

1) Representing the age of the respondent.

Age group	No. of respondents	percentage
19-25	8	11
25-35	22	31
35-45	23	33
More than 45	17	24
total	70	100

Interpretation

From the above table it is clear that 12% of respondents are of the age group of 19-25 years, 31% are of the respondents age of the group of 25-35 years and 24% are of the respondents are above 45 years of age. Therefore a majority of respondents who are selected for study are from the age group of 35-45 years.

1) Representing gender of the respondent.

Gender	No. of respondents	Percent
Male	48	69
Female	22	31
total	70	100

Interpretation

From the above data and chart it is clear that out of 70 respondents considered for study, 22 of the respondents are female and remaining 48 are male. Therefore 69% of the respondents are male.

2) Representing education of respondents.

Education Qualification	No. of respondents	Percent
Below graduation	2	3
Graduation	28	40
Post graduation	40	57
Total	70	100

Interpretations

The above chart indicates the from the respondents selected for the study, 57% of the respondents are post graduates, 40% are graduates and 3% of respondents are below graduates. Below graduates include the respondents who have done their diploma courses also. Therefore most of the respondents are post graduates.

3) Representing the working hours of the organization.

	No. of respondents	percent
Fair	9	13
Good	39	56
Very good excellent	14	20
Excellent	8	11
Total	70	100

Interpretation

The above table and chart states that in the study of 70% respondents of MRPL 56% of the respondents specify that working hours of the organization is good enough, 20% and 11% of employees specify that the working hours of the organization is very good and excellent, and remaining 13% of employees feel that the working hours of the organization is fair. Therefore we can infer that overall employees are satisfied with the working hours of the organization.

4) Representing the leave policy of the organization.

	No. of respondents	percent
Poor	8	11
Good	33	67
Very good excellent	11	16
Excellent	18	6
Total	70	100

Interpretation

The above table and chart highlights that out of the respondents for whom the questionnaires are distributed, 11% of the respondents are not satisfied with the leave policy of the organization, 67% of the respondents are neutral which means that they are satisfied with leave policy and 16% and 6% are fully satisfied with the leave policy of the organization. Therefore we can infer that majority of the respondents are satisfied with the organization leave policy.

5) Representing respondents missed out any quality time with family.

	No. of respondents	percentage
Never	10	14
Rarely	16	23
Sometimes	33	57
Always	11	6
Total	70	100

Interpretation

From the above table it is clear that 6% of them always miss, 57% of them sometimes miss, 14% of them never miss any times with their family and 23% of them miss time with their family. The respondents those who miss quality time may be the employees who work in shifts.

6) Respondents tired or depressed due to work.

	No. of respondents	percent
Never	10	14
Rarely	23	32
Sometimes	31	44
Always	6	10
Total	70	100

Interpretation

From the above table it is clear that 10 of the respondents never felt tired due to work, 23 of them rarely feel tired or depressed, 31 of them sometimes feel tired, and 6 of them always feel tired due to work. Therefore we can infer that out of the respondents selected for the study majority of the respondents rarely or sometimes get stressed due to work.

7) Representing the shift work of the employees

	No. of respondents	Percent
Never	53	76
Rarely	10	14
Sometimes	6	9
Always	1	1
Total	70	100

Interpretation

From the above table that we can understand that out of the respondents selected for study 1% of the employees always work in shift, which is from operations departments, 9% of the employees sometimes and 14% of the employees rarely work in shift and remaining 76% of the employees has never worked in shifts. Therefore majority of the respondents selected are from administration.

8) Representing the company organizing holidays and picnics.

Holidays and picnics.	No. of respondents	percent
Never	48	69
Rarely	14	20
Sometimes	8	11
total	70	100

Interpretation

The above chart highlights that out of the respondents selected for the study 69% of the employees deny, as the organization do not conduct picnics as such, and remaining 20% and 11% of the employees state that organization has conducted picnics rarely. Therefore we can infer that the company has never conducted picnics for the employees.

9) Representing the flexible working hours provide by the company.

	No. of respondents	Percent
Yes	39	56
No	31	44
Total	70	100

Interpretation

From the above table and chart it is clear that out of overall respondents selected 56% of the respondents agree that the organization provide flexible work timings, whereas 44% do not agree. Hence, most of the respondents are satisfied with the working timings may be the employees of operations department of the organization.

CONCLUSION

Over the last decades the evidence for the business benefits of work life balance policies has been grown in volume and strength. The studies show strong links between work life balance policies and reduced absenteeism and increased productivity. A starting point for firms to assess the cost effectiveness of work-life balance policies is to identify all the costs and benefits to find information to quantify the net impact of work-life balance policies. This can lead to generally pessimistic perception of the net impact of providing work-life balance policies. Work-life balance healthy and productive work-places.